

Extraction and spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum(V) as its thiocyanate complex in industrial, environmental and soil samples

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Abstract : A simple and rapid extractive spectrophotometric method for micro determination of molybdenum using thiocyanate as a complexing agent has been worked out for industrial, environmental and soil samples. The Mo^{VI}-thiocyanate complex is extracted into 2,2'-dipyridyl in chloroform. The vermilion colour of the extract is measured at λ_{\max} 505 nm against a similarly prepared reagent blank. The 1 : 4 (Mo : SCN) complex is found to be stable for more than one hour in the extract and obeys Beer's law over the concentration range of 0-11 $\mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the proposed method are found to be $1.24 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0075 \mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-2}$, respectively. A large number of cations, anions and complexing agents of major analytical importance such as Re^{VII}, Cr^{III,VI}, Cu^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{II,III}, W^{VI}, U^{VI}, V^V and platinum metals, sulphate, chloride, fluoride, bicarbonate, phosphate, tartrate and EDTA do not interfere. Only oxalate, acetate, hydrogen peroxide, tin, cobalt, bismuth, titanium, osmium and ruthenium interfered in the procedure. The method has been applied satisfactorily for the determination of molybdenum in varieties of samples.

Keywords : Molybdenum(V), extraction, thiocyanate complex, sample.

Introduction

Molybdenum and its compounds show different physico-chemical and biological properties¹, which allow it to be used widely in numerous fields of modern science, engineering and agriculture^{2,3}. Because of its vital role in enzymatic redox reactions and specific geo-chemical behavior⁴, molybdenum at trace levels is essential to all living organisms, especially plants, animals and microorganisms⁴. By adding trace amounts of molybdenum in the fertilizers, large increase in the crop yield has been observed. It has also been added in trace amounts in vitamin supplements and specialized medicines. Recent studies have shown that molybdenum is an important element in promoting healthy teeth⁵. On the other hand, excess exposure to it can result in toxicity to human beings, animals and plants^{1,6}. Molybdenum poisoning can cause severe gastrointestinal irritation with diarrhea, coma ruminants and even death from cardiac failure⁶. Thus, in view of the greater importance of the molybdenum in laboratory, industry and agriculture, a method for micro determination of molybdenum is a matter of prime concern.

The aim of our present study is to develop a simple,

rapid and direct spectrophotometric method for the trace determination of molybdenum in samples of diverse matrices. Thiocyanate^{4,7-12} has been extensively used for the colorimetric determination of molybdenum both in pentavalent and hexavalent states even though several other reagents^{5,13-17} may give better results. Most of these reagents are relatively expensive and not easily available which often complicate the process for determination in the latter stage. However, thiocyanate is comparatively less expensive and easily available. Therefore, a method for extractive spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum is proposed to overcome all these difficulties, using ascorbic acid as the reductant, thiocyanate as the complexing agent and 2,2'-dipyridyl in chloroform as extractant.

Results and discussion

In acidic medium, molybdenum(VI) formed thiocyanate complex that was extractable into various organic solvents but a large number of ions interfered. Using various reductants, molybdenum(V) obtained from molybdenum(VI) also combines with thiocyanate forming extractable complexes. However, the often used

lowvalent cations such as Sn^{II} , Ti^{IV} , Cu^{I} , Hg^{I} and Hg^{0} can not be used as reductants for molybdenum as they either formed extractable thiocyanate complexes itself or cause reduction to much lower oxidation states in some cases. Of the other reducing agents¹⁸, hydrazines required heating and hence time consuming, but ascorbic acid was found to be most suitable reductant for this purpose as it produces the single pentavalent state¹⁹ in H_2SO_4 medium easily at room temperature. It has been observed that the presence of iron(II) was necessary for maximum colour development which may be due to quantitative reduction of molybdenum from hexavalent to pentavalent state. Further, in presence of iron(II) the extraction of molybdenum(V)-thiocyanate complex was found to be quantitative. Moreover, the excess amount of ascorbic acid did not affect the formation and stability of Mo^{V} -thiocyanate complex.

Effect of varying experimental conditions on the absorbance of Mo^{V} -thiocyanate complex :

The effect of different variables on the absorbance of Mo^{V} -SCN complex was studied by taking 100 μg Mo/10 ml aqueous phase containing 1 ml of 5 M H_2SO_4 , 100 mg ascorbic acid, 1 ml of 0.01 M iron(II) and 1 ml of 2 M KSCN and extraction was carried out using 0.2% (w/v) 2,2'-dipyridyl in chloroform (10 ml) by single contact except where these parameters were themselves varied or specifically mentioned and measuring the absorbance of the extract at 505 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank. The effect of different variables were as discussed below :

Effect of the solvent : The complex was extracted into various solvents but the extraction was found to be maximum (99.2%) in case of 0.2% (w/v) 2,2'-dipyridyl in chloroform while other solvents gave relatively low extraction. The absorbance of the complex was found to be stable for more than one hour in 2,2'-dipyridyl in chloroform. It has been observed that amines of high molecular weight caused appreciable extraction but suffer from a large number of interferences. The extraction of the complex in different solvents was found to be decreasing in the order as : 0.2% (w/v) 2,2'-dipyridyl in chloroform (99.2%) > 0.2% (w/v) tribenzylamine in chloroform (98%), 0.2% (v/v) tri-*n*-octylamine in chloroform (98%) > ethyl methyl ketone (96%), isopentyl acetate (96%) > ethyl methyl ketone-chloroform (3 : 1) (95%) > isobutyl methyl ketone (93%) > butyl acetate (89%) > isopentyl alcohol (70%) > isoamyl alcohol (60%) >

diethyl ether (45%) > benzyl alcohol-chloroform (1 : 1) (30%) > chloroform \approx carbon tetrachloride \approx benzene \approx toluene (0.0%). The raffinate after single extraction was found devoid of any molybdenum content, which was confirmed by the more sensitive pyrogallol-thiocyanate method²⁰. Therefore, 2,2'-dipyridyl in chloroform was chosen as solvent for further studies.

Effect of nature and concentration of acid : The absorbance of the molybdenum-thiocyanate complex also depends upon the nature of the acid used. It was found considerably high from sulphuric acid medium and decreased in the order : H_2SO_4 > HCl > H_3PO_4 > CH_3COOH for the same (0.5 M) acidity level. Hence, H_2SO_4 was preferred for further studies. The absorbance increased with H_2SO_4 concentration reaching a plateau at 0.3–1.5 M (pH 0.1–0.5) and then decreased slightly with further rise in acidity. Therefore, 0.5 M H_2SO_4 was chosen as optimum acidity, which was attained by adding 1 ml of 5 M H_2SO_4 in each case.

Effect of ascorbic acid concentration : The absorbance of Mo^{V} -SCN complex increased with an initial increase of ascorbic acid amount and was found to be maximum for ≥ 75 mg of it. However, the quantitative (100%) extraction was achieved only in presence of iron(II), which probably played catalytic role during reduction of Mo^{VI} to Mo^{V} in presence of ascorbic acid. Therefore, 100 mg ascorbic acid was used in each case along with 1 ml of 0.01 M iron(II) solution. However, higher amounts (> 5 mg) of iron interfered during the determination of the element but not in the extraction.

Effect of iron : The role of iron(II) in the reduction of Mo^{VI} to Mo^{V} and its complexation with SCN^- is not well understood. In presence of iron(II) the colour of Mo^{V} -SCN complex formed was found to be more intense and the extraction was also quantitative. Therefore, iron(II) probably controls the reduction of Mo^{VI} to Mo^{V} and cause complete reduction thereby giving maximum colour intensity in the aqueous phase as well as in the organic phase after extraction. The order of addition of iron was very important. The extraction was found to be incomplete when either the iron(II) was not added or was added after the addition of thiocyanate. Therefore, the amount of iron(II) added should be in the concentration range of 0.001–0.01 M (i.e. 0.05–0.5 mg/ml) in the aqueous phase, because at lower concentration the extraction was incomplete and at higher levels iron(II) interferes in the determination step without affecting extraction step.

Effect of KSCN concentration : In the absence of thiocyanate, the absorbance of molybdenum was nil at 0.5 M acidity (H_2SO_4) and increased significantly with an increase in the reagent concentration. The absorbance increased to maximum with thiocyanate concentration range 1.0–0.25 M and higher concentration of it did not increase the absorbance. Therefore, 1 ml of 2 M reagent was used for further studies each time. As about 100% of SCN^- was also extracted along with molybdenum into the extract, hence its concentration in aqueous phase for second and subsequent extractions whenever necessary, was brought to optimal level (0.2 M) before making further extractions.

Effect of equilibration time : The absorbance of Mo^V -SCN complex increased significantly with equilibration time. It attained maximum value in 45–90 s and thereafter showed gradual decrease on further increasing the contact time. Hence, 60 s equilibration time was chosen as optimum time. Further, the shaking should be gentle as vigorous shaking caused difficulty in the separation of two layers.

On the basis of the above studies, the optimum conditions giving maximum and constant absorbance of Mo^V -SCN complex were incorporated into the proposed procedure.

Spectral characteristics : The absorption spectrum of the complex indicated that the colored species absorbs maximum within the range 502.4–510.4 nm whereas, the reagent blank absorbs negligibly in this region. Therefore, all the absorbance measurements are carried out at 505 nm against a similarly prepared reagent blank.

Beer's law, standard deviation and sensitivity : The absorbance of the complex shows a linear relationship with molybdenum content upto 11 $\mu g Mo ml^{-1}$ of the extract phase at 505 nm. The absorbance deviates from linearity at higher amounts of molybdenum along with the formation of violet-red sticky mass insoluble both in aqueous and organic phases. However, the optimum range of molybdenum determination that could be determined accurately was 3.14–8.1 ppm as evaluated from Ringbom plot²¹. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method were found to be $1.24 \times 10^4 dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$ and $0.0075 \mu g Mo cm^{-2}$, respectively. The relative

standard deviation for a set of ten replicate determinations of $5 \mu g Mo ml^{-1}$ was 0.007 absorbance units with a relative mean error of $\pm 0.5\%$.

Stoichiometry of the complex : The composition of the extracted species was found to be 1 : 4 (Mo : SCN) by Job's method²² of continuous variations as modified by Voshburg and Cooper²³ which has been further confirmed by mole-ratio method²⁴.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of cations, anions/complexing agents (mg/ml) on the absorbance of Mo^V -SCN complex was studied by taking 50 $\mu g Mo/ml$ of aqueous phase and keeping other conditions as mentioned in the procedure. Sulphate, chloride and bromide 20 mg each; fluoride 10 mg; thiourea and iodide 8 mg each; bicarbonate, tartrate and phosphate 5 mg each; carbonate 4 mg each; borate and disodium EDTA 2 mg each and glycerol 0.1 ml do not effect the absorbance at all. However, acetate 2 mg; oxalate 0.5 mg and 0.1 ml H_2O_2 [6% (v/v)] lowered the absorbance by more than 3%. Barium(II), Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ce^{IV} and Cr^{VI} 1.0 mg each; Fe^{III} , Au^{III} , Zn^{II} , Th^{IV} , Ag^I , Zr^{IV} and Al^{III} 0.5 mg each; Ir^{III} and Pt^{IV} 0.2 mg each did not interfere at all. Whereas, Cu^{II} 0.5 mg in presence of 8 mg thiourea; W^{VI} , V^V and Nb^V 0.2 mg each in presence of 10 mg sodium fluoride and U^{VI} 0.1 mg in presence of 2 mg disodium EDTA did not interfere. However, Sn^{II} , Co^{II} , Bi^{III} , Ti^{IV} , Os^{VIII} and Ru^{III} were found to interfere in the method. Anions/complexing agents were added well before the reduction of molybdenum except acetate, EDTA, citrate, tartrate, phosphate, fluoride and oxalate which were added after the reduction to Mo^V , as they were found to inhibit the reduction to some extent.

Applications : The wide applicability of the method is straightway shown by the analysis of a wide variety of natural samples (different type of water and soil samples), synthetic and technical samples with satisfactory results (Table 1). The method takes less than 20 min for single determination and much less for series operations. The method is quite simple, rapid and requires easily available common reagents. The proposed method has a wider Beer's law range^{4,7,9,10} and better sensitivity^{7,8,11,12,18} than the existing methods of determination of molybdenum using thiocyanate.

Table 1. Analysis of molybdenum samples by the proposed method

Sr. no.	Composition of sample		Mo found ^b (μg)
	Matrix ^a	Mo added (μg)	
1.	V (0.1), Ni (2.5), Mn (2.5)	75.0	75.01
2.	Ni (2), Cr (5), Zr (2)	19.0	18.95
3.	Mn (5), Cr (2.5), Cu (2.5)	55.0	55.00
4.	Ca (5), Zr (4), Al (4), Pt (0.1)	50.0	50.01
5.	Zn (5), Ti (2), W (2)	25.0	25.10
6.	Co (2), Ni (5), Mn (5)	10.0	10.00
7.	[Fe (0.25), Ni (2.5), Cr (0.75), W (0.2)] ^c	0.71	0.71
8.	[Fe (3), Ni (9)] ^c	2.76	2.75
9.	[Fe (8.370), Cu (0.050)] ^c	11.78	11.64
10.	BCS (261/1)	0.11% ^e	0.105 \pm 0.006% ^d
11.	BCS (219/4)	0.58% ^e	0.585 \pm 0.003% ^d
12.	Reverberatory flue dust	80.0	79.98 \pm 0.120 ^d
13.	Industrial effluent	100.0	99.0 \pm 0.065 ^d
14.	Canal water	50.0	50.2 \pm 0.040 ^d
15.	Well water	25.0	25.11 \pm 0.037 ^d
16.	Soil sample (without standard addition)	0.0	0.01 \pm 0.007 ^d
17.	Soil sample (with standard addition)	50.0	50.1 \pm 0.011 ^d

^aNumber in brackets indicates mg amounts of elements in the aliquot for analysis. ^bAverage of triplicate analyses. ^cSample no. 7, 8 and 9 are analogous to Hastelly C, Hastelly A and ferromolybdenum, respectively. ^dMean \pm relative standard deviation (n = 7). ^eCertified value.

Experimental

Molybdenum solution : A stock solution (100 $\mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount of sodium molybdate dihydrate (Thomas Baker, A.R.) in deionised water and standardized by the oxine method²⁵. Working standards at lower levels were obtained by suitable dilutions of the stock solution.

Solutions of other diverse metal ions were prepared by dissolving their commonly available salts (A.R.) in deionised water or dilute acids and were standardized by conventional methods²⁵. Lower concentrations at appropriate levels were obtained by suitable dilutions. All other reagent solutions were prepared by usual procedure.

Apparatus : An Elico SL 164 UV-Vis double beam spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched (quartz) cells was used for absorbance measurements.

Synthetic samples : Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing molybdenum solution with solutions of other diverse metal ions in suitable proportions to get the desired composition as shown in Table 1.

Steels : Steel samples (0.1 g) were dissolved as mentioned earlier²⁶ and suitable aliquots (2 ml) were taken for molybdenum separation and determination by the pro-

posed method after adding 100 mg each of ascorbic acid and sodium fluoride in each case (Table 1).

Reverberatory flue dust : Reverberatory flue dust sample (0.1 g) from copper manufacture, containing no molybdenum, was mixed with a solution of known molybdenum content and brought into solution as reported earlier²⁶. The molybdenum content in a suitable aliquot, after adding 80 mg thiourea in each case was determined by the proposed procedure (Table 1).

Industrial effluent : A solution of known molybdenum content (10 mg) was mixed with the industrial effluent sample (1 dm³) collected from the main outlet of effluents of metal industries located in twin cities – Yamuna Nagar and Jagadhari. A 10 ml aliquot of the sample solution was treated as reported earlier²⁷ and subjected to molybdenum determination by the proposed procedure (Table 1).

Canal water : To a 100 ml water sample taken from the Western Yamuna Canal (WYC) at Yamuna Nagar site, added a known amount of molybdenum (1 mg) and the solution was treated as reported earlier²⁷. An aliquot (5 ml) was subjected to analysis for molybdenum by the proposed method (Table 1).

Well water : To a 100 ml aliquot of well water added a known amount of molybdenum (0.5 mg) and brought into solution following the earlier reported²⁸ procedure. Taking 5 ml aliquot of this solution molybdenum was extracted and subjected to determination by the proposed procedure (Table 1).

Soil sample : A soil sample²⁹ (10 g) passed through 1 mm sieve was equilibrated with 50 ml of 1 N ammonium oxalate for 30 min and filtered. An aliquot (10 ml) of the filtrate was treated with 1 ml of 30% hydrogen peroxide (20 volumes) and evaporated to dryness. After this 0.5 ml of 30% H₂O₂ (20 volumes) was added to the residue and again evaporated to dryness. The residue was then mixed with 0.5 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ and 1 ml of 30% hydrogen peroxide (20 volumes) and heated to expel sulphur trioxide fumes. If the residue was not white at this stage repeated the final step until it becomes white. After this, the white residue was heated with 6 ml of 1 : 5 HCl and filtered. The residue was raised to 10 ml volume along with washings and 2 ml aliquot of this filtrate was used for determination of Mo by the proposed procedure. Another soil sample solution was prepared under the similar conditions after standard addition of molybdenum (50 µg) and subjected to determination by the proposed procedure (Table 1).

Procedure : To a 5 ml sample solution containing molybdenum ≤ 110 µg Mo and/or other ions in a 100 ml pear shaped separatory funnel, 1 ml of 5 M H₂SO₄, 100 mg ascorbic acid, 1 ml of 0.01 M iron(II) solution, 1 ml of 2 M KSCN solution and sufficient amount of deionized water to raise the final volume of the aqueous phase to 10 ml were added. The contents of the funnel were allowed to stand for 5 min after proper mixing to achieve full color development. The colored species was extracted by gentle shaking with 0.2% (w/v) 2,2'-dipyridyl in chloroform (10 ml) for 1 min. The two layers were allowed to separate and the organic phase was collected over anhydrous CaCl₂ to remove the water droplets. The absorbance of the clear organic phase was measured against similarly prepared reagent blank at 505 nm. The content of molybdenum in different samples was computed from the calibration curve. For higher amount of molybdenum (≥ 110 µg), two-step extraction was carried out with same volume of the extractant.

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